

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN, VER. 2.0

OF THE PROJECT:

BREAKTHROUGH LASER TECHNOLOGIES FOR SMART MANUFACTURING, SPACE AND BIO-TECH APPLICATIONS

Contents

1. Data Summary	2
2. FAIR data.....	2
3. Other research outputs	5
4. Allocation of resources	5
5. Data security.....	6
6. Ethics.....	6
7. Other issues	6

1. Data Summary

The project is using existing data from previous research and datasets prepared within implementation of the LasApp project. Thanks to the LasApp project, standard procedures for data management are being created, which makes it possible to refer to existing and newly created data in the future. The intention is to provide data in freely accessible formats. The table below summarizes the data types/formats generated within the project, incl. their indicative sizes:

The measured data are primarily used to improve the parameters of laser systems, including defining working conditions, describing the influence of individual parameters of laser radiation and its interaction with materials. Furthermore, the data are used to improve and repeatedly adjust individual technological processes in the production of special optical fibres and glass materials. Based on the data analysis, it is possible to create models and characteristics of the observed phenomena.

The measured data are from experimental tests, numerical simulations, or the result of using predictive models, image data from light and fluorescence microscopy, data from spectrophotometric analyses. The data are useful to the user community in the field of laser physics, space and engineering industries, biotechnological applications. Furthermore, the data are used in the field of data science and in the field of technology for the preparation and production of special optical fibres.

Type/ format	Size
ASCII text (.txt, .csv, .dat)	10s MB
Microsoft Excel/ Word (.xlsx, docx.)	100s MB
Portable document format (.pdf)	100s MB
COMSOL (.mph)	10s GB
MATLAB (.matx)	100s MB
ORIGIN PROJECT (.opj)	100s MB
Portable Gray Map Image (.pgm)	10s GB
Portable Network Graphic (.png)	100s MB
JavaScript Object Notation (.json)	100s MB
Hierarchical Data Format (.h5)	MBs
Python (.py)	MBs
Jupyter Notebook (.ipynb)	10s MB
R scripts (.R)	MBs
Tag Image File Format (.tiff)	100s MB
Open Document File (.odt)	100s MB

2. FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data, including digital objects created within the project, **will be provided with a persistent DOI identifier**, which will be automatically assigned within a trusted public repository. The relevant data are supplemented with relevant metadata, which are uploaded together with the data to the Repository and will be appropriately indexed to ensure easy traceability. Metadata will be entered in

such a way that it can be processed automatically. **Metadata will be created in accordance with the [General recommendations for metadata description](#)** according to the National Technical Library. For text result types, the metadata will be [Dublin Core](#) compliant. In the case of datasets, metadata will be stored according to the [DataCite](#) standard.

Adequate keywords will be provided with the data to maximize reuse potential, updated with any additional keywords once the data is uploaded to the repository, e.g. laser, LIDT, Ho:YAG, laser shock peening, laser welding, laser micromachining, machine learning, big data, ultrashort pulses, diode pumping, biofilms, antimicrobial effect, microstructured fibre, preform, nanocrystal, bioinformatics, interference, etc.

A standard procedure has been established for naming files: [date]_[system part]_[device description]_[conditions]_[dataset name]_[dataset no.]_[version no.]. File names will maintain clear relationships between individual data.

Open Science obligation under the OP JAK rules

In accordance with Methodological Letter No. 1 to the Rules for Applicants and Beneficiaries – Specific Part for the Excellent Research Call, Version 3, dated 2 December 2025, the beneficiary is obliged to ensure open access to **publication outputs of type J, i.e. peer-reviewed scholarly articles with the designation “article”, “review”, or “letter”** pursuant to the Methodology for the Evaluation of Research Organisations 2017+ and 2025+ (hereinafter referred to as the “article”). In the case of an article whose corresponding (lead) author is, through that article, affiliated exclusively with a foreign institution or foreign institutions, or in the case of other types of publication outputs, ensuring open access is recommended for the beneficiary.

For other types of publication outputs (e.g. conference papers published in proceedings – type D) open access is not mandatory, i.e. only recommended.

Making data accessible

Repository

In the first step, the measured data are stored within the data centres of individual partners. All open data are stored in a trusted repository. Due to the absence of a suitable branch repository and with regard to the interdisciplinary dimension of the project, in which both institutions of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic and representatives of universities are represented, in addition entities from various fields of science (e.g. laser physics, biotechnology, smart engineering), scientific publications and research data are being **stored within the universal repository Zenodo**, which is operated by the international research infrastructure CERN, or other trusted public repository according to the Open Science Procedures Manual of the OP JAC (hereinafter “the Repository”).

Data is securely stored in the Repository, provided with a detailed metadata description and persistent DOI identifiers, including the assignment of DOIs to digital objects. In the Repository, the data record is linked to the related publication results.

In the future, the consortium is also considering the use of the [National Data Repository](#) operated by CESNET, which is currently in pilot operation. The relevant representatives of the applicant/partners are members of working groups for defining standards and further development within the framework of open science in the Czech Republic. **The project envisages the use of this national infrastructure being built.**

Data

All data from which the scientific publications created within the LasApp project are freely available.

The exception for data sharing only applies if the results of the project represent a high level of innovation, i.e. possibility of commercialization of research results. In this case, the project consortium will consider two forms of protection: 1) withhold the data for internal use or 2) apply for a patent for

commercial exploitation of the invention. If such data is shared outside the project consortium, appropriate measures will be taken to protect intellectual property rights (e.g. NDA).

The decision regarding the commercialization of research results falls within the competence of the Project Steering Committee (PMC). Issues regarding the handling of intellectual property created within the project will be resolved within the Partnership Agreement concluded within the project consortium prior to the issuance of the Grant Decision.

The principle applies that all data are available as soon as possible. Scientific publications and related data are stored in the Repository no later than the day the publication is published. This means that no time embargo applies in this case.

An exception may be data that will be subject to intellectual property protection, for example: i) data that may be part of a patent application or utility model application; ii) data that will be part of a trade secret; iii) data that will be necessary to keep secret due to the high probability of their commercialization, e.g. through license agreements; In cases ad i) the data will be made available after the relevant patent application has been published. In cases ad ii) and iii), the data will be kept confidential only for the necessary time.

All data stored in the Repository are freely accessible to the public without restrictions. Apart from the above, no data usage restrictions are applied. All data are available during implementation and after the end of the project. Therefore, there is no need to establish a data access committee.

Metadata

The Repository supports sharing under Creative Commons licenses. ***All scientific publications (type "J") and research data accessible under the terms of the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International (CC BY) public license.***

All data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the Repository.

Software

As part of the LasApp project, commercially available SW (e.g. COMSOL, MATLAB, Labview) is being used, which is referenced for the relevant data to ensure full access to the data. Additionally, third-party open-source Python and R libraries that are freely available, well documented, and listed is provided. As part of the LasApp project, third-party open-source software is being used, which is freely available and well documented, and it makes no sense to include it in the generated data.

Making data interoperable

The aim is to make all the data created in the project as interoperable as possible, allowing the exchange and reuse of data between researchers, institutions, organizations, etc. The project partners are adhered to the above standards for formats that are compatible with open-source software applications source code, which will facilitate re-combinations with different datasets from different sources.

This is especially important when comparing experimental datasets with numerical results. Special attention is focused on defining a common frame of reference for all variables. These variables is described by an established engineering vocabulary (see e.g. below) to maximize data interoperability:

[Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology](#); [European Research Information Ontology](#), [Materials And Molecules Basic Ontology](#); [Ontology for Biomedical Investigations - Community Standard for Scientific Data Integration](#); Standards of the ČSN ISO 80000 series, especially ČSN ISO 80000-7 Quantities and units - Part 7: Light.

The project is not using unusual ontologies or generate project-specific ontologies/vocabularies. Data created and published within the project provides a link in their metadata to at least one other dataset published in the project with the aim of linking all data.

Increase data re-use

Methods of verification and reuse of generated data are linked to individual data formats and sources of this data. The common way of documentation is the syntax of naming data files (information about date, time, workplace, device). The next level of documentation is provided by laboratory diaries, which are stored in the Repository and whose data are linked to the generated data using indexes and metadata. If the devices or formats used allow the creation of descriptive files, header tables, the use of markup language or other methods describing data operations, this information are inserted and indexed together with the source data in the Repository.

All scientific publications (type "J") and research data are accessible under the terms of the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International (CC BY) public license. The use of a more restrictive licence (e.g. CC BY-NC-ND) is permitted where the publisher does not allow publication in open-access mode under the CC BY licence.

All data will be fully usable by third parties during the implementation and after the end of the project. The data are available for reuse immediately after publication of the relevant scientific publication. There is no embargo on the data except for limitations related to the protection of intellectual property. Data will remain in the Repository for as long as the repository operators allow, see comments above.

The origin of the data will be documented according to relevant standards, e.g. ANSI/ISO/IEC 9075:2003, "Database Language SQL"; For individual types of formats, e.g.: .xml, - ISO/IEC 19503:2005, .xlsx and .docx - ISO/IEC 29500, .csv - RFC 4180, .od* - ISO/IEC 26300:2006. In the case of automatically generated data, the W3C Prov. standard will be followed.

Within the LasApp project, **the following processes is being applied to ensure data quality:**

Coordination of data quality by the appointed Data steward - meetings/video conferences within the project consortium with the aim of ensuring quality management of project data. Principles of good laboratory practice will be observed, such as the following measures: i) repeated measurements; ii) verification of data entry; iii) file integrity check; iv) repeating critical calculations using another SW; v) Code review.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the publications and research data generated within the LasApp project, other related research results are stored in the relevant Repository.

The FAIR standards mentioned in chap. 2 above are applied on all other research outputs, with the provision that they will be stored together with the primary research outputs in the Repository. The above is applied in the LasApp project as part of the so-called optional procedures of open science. The DMP itself, as another output of the project, will be stored as a public document in the [Zenodo](#) repository.

4. Allocation of resources

The Repository is free of charge, i.e. no costs arise in connection with the storage of public data. Related copyrights with a CC BY license are also free of charge. Long-term data storage will be ensured free of charge through the Repository.

The applicant's budget includes the personal costs of a 0.1 FTE Data Steward who coordinates the Open Science agenda within the LasApp project. The personal costs are covered by the OP JAC resources.

All members of the project consortium have allocated resources within their institutional co-financing budgets for APC fees associated with publication in Gold Open Access scientific journals.

Costs related to storing data in the data centers of the applicant and individual partners are covered from their own resources.

From the beginning of the project, the **Data Steward, who is part of the applicant's expert team**, is responsible for data management. In addition, a contact person for data management is nominated within each Research Work Package, with whom the Data Steward is in close contact. These representatives **undergo special training to ensure high quality data management**.

5. Data security

The data of the applicant and partners are stored in the respective data centers of each institution, which are secured and backed up by various means. The consortium members ensure ongoing training in cybersecurity. **The project a priori does not work with sensitive data.**

The following guidelines are followed to ensure data security: i) storing data in at least two separate locations to prevent data loss; ii) restrictions on the use of USB flash drives for long term storage; iii) labelling the files in a systematically structured way to ensure the coherence of the final data set.

The Repository guarantees long-term data storage and maintenance. All data are kept here for the lifetime of the storage. In case of the Zenodo, it is currently the lifetime of the CERN host laboratory. Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated to multiple copies in an online system. Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password "hashing" algorithms.

6. Ethics

The project participants did not identify any ethical problem regarding the data, because **no experiments or the data do not concern living organisms** and no negative impact on the environment is expected, given that all experiments will be carried out in a closed and suitable facility.

The project does not use personal data in any way. For this reason, it is not relevant to deal with informed consent to processing, or by sharing data.

7. Other issues

For data management, rules and methodological recommendations will be used according to the documentation: Manual of Open Science procedures within OP JAC.